

Preserving Human Creativity: The Balance Between AI and Human Creative Abilities

The convergence of human ingenuity and artificial intelligence (AI) has led to a growing tendency for individuals to delegate creative tasks to AI. This trend has resulted in a diminishing presence of original human creativity in various spheres. As AI's creative capabilities continue to improve, a troubling disparity is unfolding: AI is thriving as a creative force, while human creative capacities are undergoing a concerning deterioration.

The boundary between human and AI creativity is rapidly blurring, prompting a fundamental shift in how we approach innovation and imaginative endeavors. While historical domains like music composition and speech generation were once the exclusive domains of human creativity, we are witnessing an unprecedented transformation. AI, once relegated to the realm of data manipulation, is now assuming roles of supreme creativity—crafting music, generating art, and formulating groundbreaking concepts.

To exemplify, let us examine a recent empirical study where assignments structured in accordance with the grandmastery[1] framework, specifically devised to cultivate and assess narrative and abstract thinking proficiencies, were allocated to Chat GPT[2], Bing[3], and Google Bard[4]. This experimental endeavor serves as an illustrative paradigm of the capabilities exhibited by artificial intelligence (AI). Through leveraging AI's narrative aptitude and introducing stochasticity via keywords and a pre-established thematic structure, the resultant outcomes were remarkably engrossing. The visual depictions of finalized tasks[5] pertaining to integrative cognitive processes, structured within the grandmastery framework, lucidly and eloquently portray the recent evolutionary trajectory of AI. This progression traverses the spectrum from fundamental data manipulation to the sophisticated craft of constructing narratives that resonate deeply with audiences.

However, amidst AI's ascension, a profound dilemma looms: the increasing reliance on AI for creative tasks is leading to a decline in human creative engagement. Tasks that once required human imagination and ingenuity are now being outsourced to AI for the sake of efficiency and convenience. This outsourcing of creative tasks to AI has fostered a sense of dependency, where individuals are gradually relinquishing their creative responsibilities. The result is a troubling decline in the exercise of human creativity, as fewer individuals engage in the act of creating themselves.

While AI's capabilities continue to evolve and expand, human creativity faces an insidious erosion. The allure of AI-driven solutions has led to a detachment from the process of original creation. As AI becomes more adept at generating music, art, and innovative ideas, the

imperative for individuals to exercise their creative faculties is diminishing. The ease with which AI can produce creative outputs has inadvertently led to a devaluation of the creative process among humans.

This shift in creative dynamics poses a profound societal challenge. As AI takes center stage in producing creative outputs, there is a risk that human creativity will fade into the background, leading to a future where fewer and fewer individuals engage in the act of genuine creation. The very essence of what it means to be a creator and innovator is at stake, as our reliance on AI threatens to relegate human creativity to the periphery.

The consequences of this trend extend beyond the individual level to the broader societal fabric. A society that places increasing reliance on AI for creative tasks risks losing touch with the authentic human experience of crafting and inventing. The vibrancy of artistic expression, the profundity of philosophical inquiry, and the richness of creative thought could all become casualties of this shift.

In a world where AI's creative capacities are on the rise, there is an urgent need to reevaluate the balance between AI-assisted creativity and human creative engagement. While AI's potential to enhance creative processes is undeniable, preserving and nurturing human creative capacities is equally crucial. The challenge is not to stifle the progress of AI, but rather to ensure that it complements, rather than replaces, human creative endeavors.

As we navigate this evolving landscape, it is imperative to recognize that the creative act is an essential aspect of human identity. The act of creation is deeply intertwined with our sense of purpose, self-expression, and innovation. Therefore, striking a harmonious coexistence between AI and human creativity is not only a technological challenge but a philosophical imperative—one that ensures that the torch of human imagination continues to burn bright amidst the burgeoning AI landscape.

[1] Grandomastery. (2023). Retrieved 14 August 2023, from <https://www.grandomastery.com/>

[2] ChatGPT. (2023). Retrieved 14 August 2023, from <https://chat.openai.com/>

[3] Bing. (2023). Retrieved 14 August 2023, from <https://www.bing.com/>

[4] Google Bard. (2023). Retrieved 14 August 2023, from <https://bard.google.com/>

[5] Popov, A. (2023). Balancing AI Advancements: Preserving Human Creativity Amidst Growing Artificial Ingenuity. Retrieved 15 August 2023, from <https://zenodo.org/record/8250794>

